

Secretive Slime Molds (Book review)

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Steve Stephenson, a research professor at the University of Arkansas in the United States, is the author of a very clear guide to Australian myxomycetes, entitled “Secretive Slime Moulds: Myxomycetes of Australia” and published in 2021 by ABRs, Canberra and CSIRO Publishing, Melbourne, Australia. Steve’s extensive knowledge of collecting and describing species over very many years has enabled him to generate interest in the newcomer to myxomycetes while also maintaining enough science to keep the professional enthusiast engrossed. This is a user-friendly guide that goes a long way towards explaining what is ‘secretive’ about myxomycetes, those intriguing microscopic eukaryotic organisms.

In Australia, very little work has been completed to determine the distribution and ecology of myxomycetes across the diverse environments of this huge continent. Australian life forms have had to adapt to constant environmental changes, brought about by millions of years of leaching of the ancient geological substrates, the dryness of the soil from sporadic rainfall, and from constant fires, both naturally occurring and man-made.

“Secretive Slime Moulds” concentrates on the microenvironment and the appearance of myxomycete fruiting bodies. Worldwide there are approximately 1,000 species of myxomycetes, and more than 330 of these are known to occur here in Australia, a total to which we are adding regularly. Steve has covered all the species recorded to date in Australia and discusses many other species similar to those he is describing, thereby giving the reader a clear, comprehensive understanding of all structural features, very beneficial when observing one’s own specimens. Although this edition contains some wonderful photographs, it is not a field guide or a book to use to “picture-match” specimens. The book is a scientific monograph of Australian species that contains references to many other publications with illustrations.

Steve provides clear summaries about the history, collections, and even laboratory work that may be carried out in the home environment. He makes this a perfect introduction to interest and encourage the reader. How satisfying to learn to read ‘Dichotomous Keys,’ to experiment with ‘Growing in Moist Chambers,’ and to begin writing scientific papers on those myxomycetes that can be found in one’s local area!

The text expands to cover the most up to date classification based on phylogeny constructed from 18S rDNA sequences (Fiore-Donne et al. 2013). The Myxomycetes, for instance, are broken into two

subclasses, the Lucisporomycetidae, light spored, and Columellomycetidae, dark spored clades, which consist mostly of members of the traditional orders plus many newly recognized orders as outlined by Ukraine researcher Dmitry Leontyev et al. (2019).

With more citizen scientists becoming interested in these amazing creatures, we are discovering many more of them, more frequently, particularly in times of regenerative rainfall. The reasoning behind this phenomenon is clearly explained in the commentary on the 'Life Cycle of Myxomycetes' in Steve's wonderful book "Secretive Slime Moulds."

This publication deserves the highest recommendation. Steve's love for this topic and his enthusiasm over many years for the environment is profound. The book is available from CSIRO or from Amazon.

References

Fiore-Donno AM, Clissmann F, Meyer M, Schnittler M, Cavalier-Smith T. 2013. Two-gene phylogeny of bright-spored myxomycetes (slime moulds, Superorder Lucisporidia). PLoS ONE. 8(5): e62586.

Leontyev DV, Schnittler M, Stephenson SL; Novozhilov YK. 2019. Towards a phylogenetic classification of the Myxomycetes. Phytotaxa. 399 (3): 209-238.